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Peer Review Procedures in Higher Education applied to Engineering Studies

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ABSTRACT

The peer review procedure is based on a mutual exchange process of giving and receiving feedback from people with similar competences. Set in the context of higher education, it is a specific form of peer learning, where the solution proposal of an exercise and the feedback comes from students attending the same course.

Using the peer review process, individual feedback for all students can be generated, even for large courses, under reasonable effort for the teachers. It enables students to reflect on their own solutions and share their knowledge, which is mutually beneficial.

A challenge when applying the technique to new courses or study fields lies in developing suitable tasks. It should be possible to cope with the assessment of the tasks at a satisfying quality level and in reasonable time, providing beneficial learning effects to both the reviewer and the reviewee.

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In this contribution, we revisited the technique with the aim to provide new ideas for applications in civil engineering education and to improve existing ones. We applied three different types of tasks and evaluation schemes to a peer review procedure in the context of a fundamental undergraduate course with about 500 attendees. We statistically evaluated the exam results and observed an upward deviation in the grades of the participants in the peer review procedure. Additionally, we determined the acceptance amongst the participants using a questionnaire. Based on our experiences, we make proposals for using peer review procedures in engineering education.

1 INTRODUCTION

The peer review procedure is based on a mutual exchange process of giving and receiving feedback from people with similar competences [1]. Peer review procedures are conventionally used in scientific publications, where experts in the relevant research field of a particular publication evaluate the contents with respect to credibility. Its main purpose is to ensure the quality of a published text. Also on a professional level, peer review is common practice, as for example clinical or technical peer review.

Set in the context of higher education, peer review is a specific form of peer learning [2], where the solution proposal of an exercise and the feedback comes from students attending the same course and therefore having roughly the same level of experience in that topic, instead of feedback given by the teaching staff. The idea behind adapting specific aspects of peer learning in higher education is that learning from each other is not limited to informal learning. The ability of developing skills on our own is something engineers are confronted with regularly in everyday working life. It is also something already taking place in university life, on an informal as well as on a formal level.

Introducing the peer assessment procedures in the fundamental pre-graduate lecture “Technical Mechanics in Civil Engineering” was based on the ideas of Boud et al. [2]. They state that the reciprocal learning process is not necessarily incidental, but rather can be actively promoted. Although this was not the main intention, reducing the workload on the part of the teaching staff also played a role in these considerations.

2 BENEFITS OF USING PEER REVIEW IN HIGHER EDUCATION

According to literature, different models of peer learning can be identified, for example

- proctor models, where peer tutoring seniors teach juniors [3],
- discussion seminars,
- collaborative project and group works,

to name only a few of them. Topping [4] mentioned some examples of peer tutoring adapted to higher education and already stated the beneficial learning effects of this method.

Whereas the above mentioned methods aim to provide an exchange of knowledge between students [4] or encourage discussions, peer review procedures in higher education context urge students to evaluate the work of other peers [1], e.g. in form of a written feedback. It can be distinguished from peer assessment, which aims to grade the work of a peer [5]. Using the peer review process, individual feedback for

all students can be generated, even for large courses, under reasonable effort for the teachers. It enables students to reflect on their own solutions and share their knowledge, which is mutually beneficial [2].

A former study by Nicol et al. [1] showed that using peer review procedures in education can reduce the necessity of external feedback. The same study also refers to national surveys in the UK and Australia, highlighting that feedback is one of the key elements identified by students to lack during their studies.

3 ON THE CURRENT USE OF PEER REVIEW IN HIGHER EDUCATION

Peer review is well established in medicine and legal studies, and in recent times has been adapted to various study fields, including engineering education. Reported applications in engineering studies often focus on particular types of tasks like design processes, programming skills, writing skills or laboratory reports as some of the more common ones.

A well-documented example of using peer assessment methods in engineering education deals with a single midterm task in the context of an electrical engineering undergraduate course as described by Boud et al. [7]. This also served as a template to our first try to adopt the procedure in our courses. A more recent study of using peer review procedures in an Informatics course is given by Conde et al. [8]. Andersson et al. [9] contribute an application of a peer review process of laboratory reports for engineering students, focusing on the classification scheme for the reviewing.

Mulder et al. [6] presented a study on students' perception of peer review in higher education, highlighting some of the difficulties that arise. Studies determining the learning mechanism behind peer review procedures, as in Cho et al. [10] and Nicol et al. [1], state that the examination and critical review of peer texts provide a better understanding of the topic. Even though mainly aimed at writing skills or product design as in Nicol et al. [1], in our opinion this effect seems to hold true also for calculation tasks, as they are common in engineering education. Now the question arises, how the same ideas can be adopted to theoretical tasks, such as mathematical solution procedures or calculated results.

One challenge lies in developing suitable tasks, which can be assessed with satisfying quality in reasonable time, providing beneficial learning effects to both the reviewer and the reviewee.

Besides this, our experiences showed that well suited incentive systems are favourable measures in order to motivate the students to take part in the peer review procedure, in case participation is not mandatory anyhow.

4 TECHNICAL LAYOUT OF THE PEER REVIEW PROCESS

One important challenge of the introduction of a peer review procedure in fundamental lectures with a great amount of course attendants is the administration. The additional workload for supervising the peer review procedure has to be kept low. Additionally, a high quality of the assessment and the accompanying feedback has to be ensured, especially if an incentive system is offered.

Fig. 1. Layout of the peer review procedure in Moodle

In the given study, the participants were guided through the peer process by using the integrated tools of the open-source learning management system (LMS) Moodle, which was developed in 2001. Here, a complete automatization of the submission and assessment process, a random distribution amongst the participants and returning the individual feedback is possible. The main interface is shown in Fig. 1. The quality of the given feedback can be ensured by comparing different feedbacks against each other, verifying that the discrepancy between them is within an acceptable range.

5 CONTENTUAL LAYOUT OF THE PEER REVIEW PROCESS

In this research, we compare different types of tasks and assessment schemes applied to a peer review process in the context of engineering science in fundamental theoretic lectures, in particular on the example of the course “Technical Mechanics in Civil Engineering”. Two types of tasks are examined in depth and the results are evaluated qualitatively by means of comparing the grades of participants and non-participants as well as the assessment of a questionnaire amongst the participants on learning benefits, time effort, conception of the tasks, assessment of the tasks and quality of the received feedback.

We applied the peer review procedure to the following tasks:

- Case 1: Mid-term exam
- Case 2: 14 weekly task sheets, prepared and discussed in tutor groups
- Case 3: Ongoing study project with practical relevance, distributed in three task sheets

In all cases, the students had to process the given tasks, upload their solution in the open source learning management system (LMS) Moodle, scrutinise solutions of fellow students and upload the assessed solution in Moodle. Afterwards, they received feedback from their peers. Depending on the case, the peers could be one or more students attending the same course. In order to create a safer environment for the students, i.e. to minimize anxiety and stress caused by the peer review process, we kept the feedback anonymous, as recommended by Andersson et al. [9].

The participation in the peer review procedures was voluntarily due to legal constraints. To increase the students’ motivation to participate in the offered peer

review procedure, in case 2 (weekly task sheets) and case 3 (ongoing study project) we provided an incentive system. This included a grade improvement of 0.3 (1.0 best, 5.0 worst mark) in case of a successful participation. Thereby, a successful participation meant, that the students have passed 75% of the issued task sheets including an additional mid-term. The task sheets and the mid-term were passed, if the processing was good, e.g. a minimum of 50% of the points available had been achieved and the evaluation of the fellow students' task sheets was reasonable.

In the following, the three investigated cases are described in detail:

Case 1: In a first trial, we started by using a peer review procedure to evaluate a mid-term exam. The exam was held during lecture time and mainly served as a preparation for the final exam. Therefore, the tasks closely resembled those of the final exam with respect to complexity, level of difficulty and degree of abstraction. With a rough number of 500 course attendants it would not have been possible for the teaching staff to evaluate thoroughly the students' solutions. However, by using the peer review procedure to assess the mid-term exam, detailed feedback could be created for every student. After solving the exam, students uploaded their own solution in Moodle and randomly were assigned to one fellow student's work for reviewing. For the reviewing process a detailed solution proposal with a suitable point scheme, several comments and additional hints existed. Thus, the students could be motivated to reflect on their solution and a detailed assessment of the mid-term exam was possible. As a result of the peer assessment, the students received the peer's comments on their processed tasks and a grade. The grade was calculated by the peers in a similar manner as this is done in the final exam. Each task is rated and weighted due to its percentage of the total score of the mid-term exam. The grade didn't account for the final course grade due to legal constraints, but it provided the participants a fair estimation on their current state of knowledge. By this means, we tried to encourage the students to catch up with lecture contents, before it would be too late. With only 21 participants in the first year and 62 in the second the acceptance was way below our expectations.

Case 2: In the second trial, we adopted the process to weekly task sheets (*Fig. 2*), the students were encouraged to solve during the semester. The task sheets so far had been discussed and supervised in a well approved system of peer tutoring [4] in fixed weekly slots. As in the case of the mid-term exam, the teaching staff could not handle the expenses to evaluate every student's task sheet and give individual feedback. Now, we decided to adapt the already tested peer review procedure to those weekly task sheets, introducing the described incentive system for increasing the motivation for participation in the peer review procedure. The used tasks were rather abstract and theoretic. Again, the students had to solve the task sheets and upload their proposed solution. For the assessment, the peers obtained a detailed solution of the task sheet. To avoid disproportionate correction effort, the students used a very coarse evaluation scheme. The peers had to decide whether the solution is mostly correct (2 points), partly correct with a mechanically reasonable approach (1 point) or insufficient (0 points) for each single task. To ensure the quality of the assessment - respectively the peer's feedback - each student had to evaluate the task sheets of three fellow students. Thus, different feedbacks could be compared and verified by the discrepancy between them. This is done in Moodle automatically.

Fig. 2. Exemplarily task sheet as used for the second adaption of the peer review procedure

Case 3: In the third adaption of the peer review procedure, we varied the task once again by offering a lower number of task sheets. This included longer processing and assessment periods. Additionally, the tasks were less abstract and theoretical examples, but rather an ongoing study project (Fig. 3) with practical relevance to show the students how the taught methods can be used in a real engineering context, here for example for the designing of bridges. Besides the offer of a grade improvement for a successful participation in the peer review procedure, the practical application was used for a further enhancement of the students' motivation. While creating suitable tasks, it was important to find a balance between complexity of the problem to be solved and a restriction of possible solutions for the reviewer to be capable of producing qualitative feedback within considerable time and without immoderate effort for the assessment. On the other hand, tasks with a variety of possible solution strategies should be created, as the understanding and correction of different approaches might enhance the peer's learning effect. The peer procedure itself did not differ from case 2, described above. Only the assessment had to be done finer than in case 2. The peers were distributed a point scheme for their correction, together with a detailed solution of the tasks including comments and some varying solution strategies. The submission is rated due to its percentage of the total score of the task sheet and then assigned to a rather fine percentage scheme divided in steps of 10 percent. Additionally, there was the option to give a personal written feedback.

Fig. 3. Extract of the ongoing project used for the third adaption of the peer review procedure

6 EVALUATION AND FINDINGS

The different peer review methods have been evaluated using a survey on students' experiences, as well as assessing their overall performance in the final exam. Significant improvement of the grades of those students participating in the peer process could be observed in the second and third case, whereas we did not statistically evaluate case 1 due to the limited number of participants. In the course "Technical Mechanics 1", where we employed case 3, the mean grade of the exam was 3.43, with a grading scale reaching out from 1.0 to 5.0 and a minimum of 4.0 needed to pass the course. From 500+ course attendees a total number of 446 students took the exam. Fig. 4 shows the distribution of the grades for those 145 students, who successfully participated in the peer review procedure, in the following indicated as "Group 1", and those 301 students, who did not participate or succeed, indicated as "Group 2", separately.

The mean grade for "Group 1" was 2.49, with a standard deviation of 1.03. For "Group 2" we could identify a large downward deviation, with a mean grade of 3.88 and a standard deviation of 1.04. For "Group 1" 92.42% of the students attending the exam passed it, whereas in "Group 2" only 51.50% passed.

Fig. 4. Distribution of grades – Case 3

Fig. 5. Distribution of grades – Case 2

The same data is shown for the course “Technical Mechanics 2”, where we applied case 2 (Fig. 5), with 241 students of the relevant year, that took the exam. Once again, Fig. 5 displays the grades separately for those 78 students that did participate in the peer review procedure, indicated as “Group 3”, and those 163 students that did not (“Group 4”). In accordance with the other results, the mean grade showed a downward deviation for “Group 4” as compared against “Group 3”. The complete comparison of the mean grades and standard deviation is given in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean grade and standard deviation for different groups of students

	Case 2			Case 3		
	all	“Group 3”	“Group 4”	all	“Group 1”	“Group 2”
mean grade	3.71	2.98	3.86	3.43	2.49	3.88
standard deviation	0.93	1.04	0.81	1.22	1.03	1.04
mean grade (passed)	3.18	2.73	3.34	2.72	2.34	3.06
standard deviation (passed)	0.91	0.93	0.77	1.16	0.91	1.16

The survey was conducted in the course, where the third peer review case was applied. The used five point Likert-Scale had ordered response levels starting with 1 – “strongly disagree” and ending with 5 – “strongly agree”. In the following we present the main findings of the evaluation of the survey along 124 course attendants. After restricting on those surveys of students that participated in the peer review procedure and excluding contradictory answers, a total of 93 surveys was left. Amongst those,

85 students claimed to have received a bonus, thus successfully participated in the peer review procedure from beginning to the end, whereas 8 students answered negative on this question, mostly arguing that they aborted their participation due to a too high time effort. Of all participants of the survey, only 7 have made previous experiences with peer reviewing. *Table 2* shows the mean levels and the percentage of students that agreed with a statement exemplarily for selected questions.

Table 2: Results of the survey

		Mean level	Percentage of agreement
I.5	The time effort for the peer review procedure compared to learning benefits is justified.	3.33	43.01%
II.4	By solving the tasks, I could improve my understanding of the course content.	4.10	79.35%
III.4	By reviewing the work of peers, I could improve my understanding of the course content.	2.72	26.88%
IV.5	The received feedback improved my understanding of the course content.	2.13	7.87%
I.6	I can imagine a voluntary participation in a similar activity.	2.18	11.83%
I.7	I generally support the idea of reviewing and receiving feedback from peers.	3.50	54.84%
I.8	I would like to have more similar activities during my further studies.	3.74	61.29%
II.1	The tasks served as additional motivation to deal with the course content.	3.95	66.30%
III.3	I feel confident to review and grade peers.	4.12	80.43%
IV.1	The received grading, to my opinion, was fair.	3.85	74.19%
IV.2	The received grading, to my opinion, was correct.	3.74	68.48%
IV.3	The received feedback and comments were useful.	2.64	17.98%
IV.4	The received feedback was comprehensible.	2.99	28.89%
V.4	During work, I received sufficient support throughout a tutor or teacher.	3.89	67.05%

Fig. 6 shows the time effort needed for the solution of the task sheets as estimated by the participants. Referring to the median, the estimated time effort lies around 8-10 hours per task sheets with a total number of 4 task sheets. This value corresponds more or less to the time effort related to 1 ECTS-Credits in a module with a total of 8 ECTS-Credits. The figure also shows that the time spent on solving the tasks was slightly higher than the time for reviewing.

Fig. 6. Time requirements as estimated by the participants

Asking if the total time effort was justified compared against the learning benefits, 43% agreed, whereas only 20% disagreed. No significant deviation could be identified for this value between those students receiving a bonus and those that did not. 79% of the students agreed, that they could improve their understanding of the course contents by solving the task sheets. The survey also showed, that almost one third of the students (27%) perceived a learning benefit from giving feedback. This feeling is in accordance with the results presented in a study of Cho et al. [10] in an undergraduate laboratory physics course. In this study the beneficial effects of reviewing laboratory reports on the quality of written text are determined. Compared to the approval rates to learning benefits from solving and reviewing the tasks, the approval of learning benefits from the received feedback was rather low with a value of just 8%. The reason for that might result from the form of feedback expected to pass the peer review procedure. Some comments of students mentioned that forcing participants to give a more detailed feedback would have been desirable. Concerning the perception of learning benefits in either of the three steps no correlation to the final grade could be identified. Weaker and stronger students felt pretty much similar about the learning benefits of the peer review procedure without any clear deviation in the survey that needs to be mentioned.

Despite the rather low agreement concerning beneficial learning effects of the received feedback, 74% of the participants perceived it to be fair and 68.48% claimed the feedback and assessment to be correct. Nevertheless, only 29% of the participants evaluate the received feedback to be comprehensible and an even lower percentage (18%) agreed that the received feedback and comments were usefull. This clearly highlights the necessity to train the ability to create and interpret feedback.

Concerning the used tasks, two third of the participants considered them as motivation to address the course content. Nevertheless, only 12% could imagine a purely voluntary participation in such an activity. Therefore, incentive systems seem to be inevitable, if a compulsory participation is not possible due to e.g. legal constraints.

Looking at the overall acceptance of the procedure, as already mentioned, 43% claimed the measure to have positive effects on their learning. 54% agreed that the general idea of assessing their peer's work is good and 61% answered that they

would like to have similar activities more often during their upcoming studies. It also deserves to be mentioned that 80% of the participants felt good about reviewing and grading their peers.

Beside the quantitative evaluation and the feedback given by the students, one important aspect needs to be mentioned: In both the second and the third peer review adaption, accompanying office hours have been offered to the students, to come together and discuss their solution as well as the received feedback. Whereas we could recognize only a minor interest in these office hours during the second adaption, the third run showed a tremendous interest of the students on the project as the task left more space for interpretation. In this way, students were encouraged to invest plenty of additional time to question and discuss contents and set focus on particular aspects of the tasks.

7 SUMMARY AND OUTLOOK

The high level of acceptance amongst the students shows, that contrary to existing concerns, the method can be adopted to engineering studies even on a theoretic level and also for other skills than writing texts. Encouraging participation going further than the original task is beneficial with respect to the exchange and discussion that might arise.

To keep the workload within acceptable bounds and to ensure the quality of the given feedback in all cases a solution proposal was distributed before the peer process started. The correction template for the evaluation in all cases was rather detailed, allowing little space for interpretation. Referring to the aspect of developing the skills “to judge the accuracy of information we receive” [2] as well as reflecting and discussing differing solutions, these aspects are not exploited completely. Nevertheless, the participants were encouraged to comprehend and reproduce different solution strategies for the same task. In order to assess the variation in the final grades of the group of students that attended and those that did not attend the peer-review process, the correlation between the improvement of the grades and the participation in the peer-procedures still has to be investigated in detail.

In the processes incorporated so far, a possibility to apply the received feedback to improve the work as mentioned in Nicol et al. [1] is still missing. This definitely includes additional potential to the acceptance and enhances the benefits for the feedback receiver. Also, a self-assessment of their own work could provide additional benefits to the students, especially when it comes to reflecting their own solution.

To conclude, the positive feedback and broad acceptance amongst the students encourages to further enhance the use of such methods in higher education purposes, keeping in mind that the tasks have to be chosen carefully to avoid superfluous work.

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